

Aerospace Robotics In Supermaneuverable Flight - Defining The Set of Attainable Motion Fields In Existing Aircraft and Motion Simulators

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Abstract

By viewing an aircraft as a special case of an Aerospace Robotics System, a procedure for quantifying supermaneuverable flight can be developed. The goal is to relate and compare existing motion fields from flight test data of supermaneuverable aircraft to the motions that can be produced by ground based flight simulators. A literature survey of existing supermaneuverable flight test data is first conducted as it relates to the linear and rotational motion fields that a pilot would be exposed to. These motion fields specify what is desired to be imitated on current aircraft simulators to replicate agile aircraft flight. Also of interest in this existing data base is its relationship to the human tolerance limits where medical risk will become a factor and thus impact the pilot's ability to perform his mission.

Introduction

Techniques developed within Aerospace Robotics can be used to help analyze aircraft in supermaneuverable flight. This is accomplished by viewing the rotational and acceleration stresses affecting the pilot as a motion field generated at an end-effector of a motion simulator (or robot). In recent years, the study of supermaneuverable aircraft has been of considerable interest due to the types of tactics that now occur in combat, which have changed significantly. Combat tactics have changed primarily due to the high technology that exists in sensors and weapon systems today. The F-22 is an example of an aircraft destined to fly in the unusual or supermaneuverable flight regime. In order to test pilots and equipment in these unusual flight scenarios, motion simulators need to replicate these untoward acceleration and rotational motion fields using multiple degrees of freedom. Knowing the desired motion

fields to be simulated impacts how flight simulators (when modeled as robotic systems) should be designed and controlled.

This paper first discusses the extant data available from supermaneuverable flight. These data are

obtained from X aircraft, analysis of video tapes of international airshows, and from prototype aircraft testing of F-15's. Secondly, the existing capability of present day motion simulators is quantified and evaluated. The capability of a motion simulator to generate a specified motion field is predicated on the number of its' available degrees of freedom and other kinematic variables as well as the dynamic parameters which include the actuator torque, inertia, friction, gravity, and other effects. Finally, the limits of human tolerance are specified where there is no known medical risk which may compromise the ability of the pilot to perform a mission. Excessive environmental stress exceeding these motion field limits may add medical risk which needs to be considered in this analysis.

The data available from supermaneuverable flight can be obtained from several sources. For example at the Armstrong Laboratory, data have been collected from high angle of attack flights of X-29 aircraft. Another source of this information is analysis of the SU-27 during performance at the 1989 Paris International Air Show and through computer simulations. A third source of this flight test data can be gleaned from F-15 simulations of prototype aircraft. The F-15 simulations have been conducted in a joint USAF-Israel study [1] whereas the prototypes fly supermaneuvers such as the negative and positive "Cobra" and the "Herbst's maneuver". These prototypes, flown in Israel, had their inertias scaled dynamically to respond to conditions of the actual

aircraft in these types of agility scenarios. Reference [2] demonstrates one of the first attempts to model a motion simulator within the context of a robotic system and to use the technology developed within robotics to better control flight simulators with respect to agile flight. First a literature survey of existing flight test data from supermaneuverable aircraft will be conducted to set the stage for what would be an ideal simulation of agile flight.

Extant Data From X-Aircraft and Other Sources:

Data are being collected from a variety of X aircraft which include the X-31 with NASA [3,4,5] and the Air Force [6]. The X-29 program has flown high angle of attack missions up to 67 degrees alpha [7,8,9] to study maneuverability issues. NASA Ames is also flying a Navy F/A-18 in wind tunnel tests [10] at high angle of attack to investigate thrust vectoring, stability, and controllability of such aircraft. Sometimes [11] the term HARV (High Angle of Attack Research Vehicle) is used to describe this program. The early work which sensationalized aircraft agility was the performance of the "Cobra" supermaneuver at the 1989 Paris Air Show [12]. This led to F-16 computer simulations of this agile aircraft demonstration [13] to analyze the possibility of US aircraft to replicate this type of flight scenario.

A small amount of data from some X-29 flights at high angle of attack [7] is presented in the sequel. These data are a small subset of some the existing X aircraft data, but they give a basic idea of the levels of linear accelerations and rotation rates that have been recorded to this date.

For consistency, and final consolidation of the data to be presented, a body axis coordinate system (figure (1)) will be used which is the main concern for acceleration research. It is primarily the stresses felt at the human body that are of interest for human factor studies when comparisons are made between different aircraft flight scenarios and their respective motion simulations.

The motion simulator used in Armstrong Laboratory is a three axes centrifuge simulator depicted in figure (2). The last two axes (cab and fork) both have rotation rates of ± 180 degrees per second. The 19 foot radius arm can move up to 56 RPM which is far beyond human tolerances.

Two flights are selected from [7] for angle of attack (AOA) $\alpha \geq 38$ degrees for presentation here. Both the Euler angles and the rigid aircraft body axis coordinate systems are utilized [14]. In this notation $p(t)$ refers to roll angle rate, $q(t)$ refers to pitch angle rate, and $r(t)$ is the yaw angle rate. The Euler attitude angles include $\psi, \theta,$ and ϕ and are easily related to the aircraft's body axes angle rates (p, q, r) through kinematic methods [14] and are displayed in figure (3). Other useful procedures [14] include the directional cosine matrix to transform variables (position, velocity, force) between one coordinate system to another. Also a commonly used representation is the "Four Parameter Quaternion" method which is helpful to reduce singularities (e.g. when the pitch attitude reaches 90 degrees).

Data from two flights of the X-29 are now summarized to get a perspective on the type of stress levels a pilot would be exposed to during these supermaneuvers. In both data sets, ϕ_b is bank angle in degrees, ψ_h is heading angle in degrees, θ_p is pitch angle in degrees, p is aircraft roll angle rate in degrees/sec, q is pitch rate in degrees/sec, r is yaw rate in degrees/second, \dot{q} is pitch acceleration in degrees/second², \dot{p} is roll acceleration in degrees/second², and \dot{r} is yaw acceleration in degrees/second². The altitude is given in feet and one G unit corresponds to 1 gravity unit = 32.2 ft/s/s.

X-29 Data, $\alpha = 38$ degrees AOA Flight 82, Condition 2 - Tracking

-92.2 deg/s ²	$\leq \dot{q} \leq$	74.5 deg/s ² (1)
-232.8 deg/s ²	$\leq \dot{p} \leq$	112.2 deg/s ² (2)
-12.8 deg/s ²	$\leq \dot{r} \leq$	22.1 deg/s ² (3)
.1 G	$\leq G_x \leq$.54 G (4)
.95 G	$\leq G_z \leq$	3.52 G (5)
-.96 G	$\leq G_y \leq$.66 G (6)
-85.7 deg	$\leq \phi_b \leq$	173.9 deg (7)
-41.4 deg	$\leq \theta_p \leq$	35.8 deg (8)
-179.8 deg	$\leq \psi_h \leq$	177.8 deg (9)
-16.5 deg/s	$\leq p \leq$	24.1 deg/s (10)
.32 deg/s	$\leq q \leq$	11.0 deg/s (11)
-11.8 deg/s	$\leq r \leq$	3.2 deg/s (12)
20,897 ft.	$\leq \text{altitude} \leq$	31,367 ft. (13)

**X-29 Data, $\alpha = 50$ degrees AOA
Flight 27 - Directional Control Check**

$$\begin{aligned}
 -44.7 \text{ deg/s}^2 &\leq \dot{q} \leq 47 \text{ deg/s}^2 & (14) \\
 -252.9 \text{ deg/s}^2 &\leq \dot{p} \leq 289 \text{ deg/s}^2 & (15) \\
 -67.4 \text{ deg/s}^2 &\leq \dot{r} \leq 69 \text{ deg/s}^2 & (16) \\
 .04 G &\leq G_x \leq .18 G & (17) \\
 .41 G &\leq G_z \leq 1.1 G & (18) \\
 -.16 G &\leq G_y \leq .23 G & (19) \\
 -110.4 \text{ deg} &\leq \phi_b \leq 133.3 \text{ deg} & (20) \\
 -66.5 \text{ deg} &\leq \theta_p \leq 25 \text{ deg} & (21) \\
 -161.2 \text{ deg} &\leq \psi_h \leq 178.5 \text{ deg} & (22) \\
 -33.3 \text{ deg/s} &\leq p \leq 1.7 \text{ deg/s} & (23) \\
 -12.8 \text{ deg/s} &\leq q \leq 1.8 \text{ deg/s} & (24) \\
 -26.4 \text{ deg/s} &\leq r \leq 2.8 \text{ deg/s} & (25) \\
 25,357 \text{ ft.} &\leq \text{altitude} \leq 37,460 \text{ ft.} & (26)
 \end{aligned}$$

The next data to be presented were obtained from the supermaneuver the "Cobra" at the 1989 Paris Air Show.

Extant Data From The 1989 Paris Air Show:

A video tape of the 1989 Paris Air Show was analyzed frame by frame when the SU-27 performed the "Cobra" supermaneuver. Analysis of these data was also kept consistent with the computer simulation given in [13]. Figure (4) demonstrates the "Cobra" as described in [13]. The following variables describe the rotational and linear variables of the centrifuge simulator in figure (2) that would produce a similar motion field stress to act on the pilot.

for $t \in [0, 5]$.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \text{Roll Rotation} &= \theta_3(t) = \frac{\pi}{180} [30 - 2t] \\
 \text{for } t \in [5, 10] &= \frac{\pi}{180} [10 + 2t] & (27)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\text{Yaw Rotation} = 0.0 \quad (28)$$

$$\text{Pitch Rotation} = -\theta_2(t) = \frac{\pi}{3} [1 - \cos(\frac{\pi t}{5})] \quad (29)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \omega_1(t) &= \dot{\theta}_1(t) = 8.8 - .56t \\
 &\text{in RPM for } t \in [0, 5] & (30)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \omega_1(t) &= \dot{\theta}_1(t) = 5.5 + .66t \\
 &\text{in RPM for } t \in [5, 10] & (31)
 \end{aligned}$$

where $\theta_1(t)$ and $\omega_1(t)$ refers to the arm axis of the centrifuge in figure (2), $\theta_2(t)$ is the fork axis, and $\theta_3(t)$ is the cab. These angles are expressed in radians. From equations (27-31), one can calculate the extreme rotational values as follows:

$$0 \text{ deg} \leq \phi_b(t) \leq 45 \text{ deg} \quad (32)$$

$$-45 \text{ deg/sec} \leq \dot{\phi}_b(t) \leq 45 \text{ deg/sec} \quad (33)$$

$$0 \text{ deg} \leq \theta_p(t) \leq 120 \text{ deg} \quad (34)$$

$$-60 \text{ deg/sec} \leq \dot{\theta}_p(t) \leq 60 \text{ deg/sec} \quad (35)$$

The linear G accelerations (only G_x and G_z were nonzero in this simulation) are influenced by the following 3 factors:

- (1) The attitude change of the aircraft and its relationship to the gravity vector.
- (2) The deceleration of the aircraft and subsequent acceleration during the pitch up and pitch down motion.
- (3) The G forces induced when the pilot is displaced from the center of rotation of the aircraft and his distance from this center of rotation.

Taking all these factors into consideration, the following extremes on the linear acceleration variables can be obtained. Please note figure (5) which is a plot of the G_x and G_z variables and figure (6) which shows a total G vector acting on the pilot ($G_{total} = \sqrt{(G_x)^2 + (G_z)^2}$) during this supermaneuver.

$$-2.5 G \leq G_x \leq 2.2 G \quad (36)$$

$$-1.0 G \leq G_z \leq 3.0 G \quad (37)$$

The next data set is derived from F-15 prototypes flown in a joint US-Israel effort [1].

Data From F-15 Prototypes Flown In Israel

Data are now reported using 1/7 th size F-15 prototypes flown in Israel as part of a joint USAF-Israel effort. These prototypes were instrumented both with lightweight accelerometers and also with rate gyroscopes to measure angular velocities and linear accelerations of the prototypes during supermaneuverable flight. It was necessary to match the radius of gyration of the prototypes to that of the F-15 under similar flight conditions. The rotations and accelerations were determined at the cockpit of the aircraft. The models flew for about 3 minutes

for each flight and extensive testing was conducted on the ground to determine the model's three polar moments of inertia. The obvious need for dynamic scaling is a consequence of the fact that the models weighed only 34 pounds (about 1/100 th of the value of the comparable F-15) but in terms of linear length scaling, the prototype was 1/7th the size (9 feet in length) of the F-15. The method of scaling the polar moments of inertia followed the classic work by Woodcock [15] and similar equations were developed by the Israel research team.

Measurements were made of $(\alpha, \beta, \theta, p, q, r, v)$ at the assumed pilot's station. The F-15 RPV had operating rudders, pushrod stabilators, and a thrust vectoring nozzle [16]. Sixteen channels of data were collected for about 3 minutes in RAM on a 286 on-board computer. These data were then down loaded at the end of a run.

The prototypes were able to reach +70 to -45 degrees alpha for tests of the positive and negative Cobra, the Herbst's maneuver, and two other supermaneuvers. The pitch excursions during these supermaneuvers were ± 120 deg. The following data describe the results in [1] when scaled dynamically to the actual F-15 inertial parameters:

$$-0.2 G < G_z < 4.6 G \quad (38)$$

$$-.5 G < G_x < 0.3 G \quad (39)$$

$$G_y \approx 0 \quad (40)$$

$$-120 \text{ deg} \leq \theta_{pitch} < 120 \text{ deg} \quad (41)$$

$$-170 \text{ deg/sec} < \dot{\theta}_{pitch} < 170 \text{ deg/sec} \quad (42)$$

For the Herbst's maneuver, (α varied from -65 deg to 70 deg angle of attack) the following range of stress variables were reported:

$$0.5 G < G_z < 4.6 G \quad (43)$$

$$-1 G < G_x < 0.5 G \quad (44)$$

$$-130 \text{ deg/sec} < \dot{\theta}_{pitch} < 100 \text{ deg/sec} \quad (45)$$

$$-150 \text{ deg/sec} < p < 40 \text{ deg/sec} \quad (46)$$

Two other supermaneuvers were run (Vectoring Only Pitch SACOMs and Elevator - Only Pitch SACOMs). The following overall limits were obtained across all 4 supermaneuvers:

$$-50 \text{ deg} < \alpha < 70 \text{ deg} \quad (47)$$

$$-170 \text{ deg/sec} < \dot{\theta}_{pitch} < 180 \text{ deg/sec} \quad (48)$$

$$-2 G < G_z < 7 G \quad (49)$$

$$-1.7 G < G_x < 0.3 G \quad (50)$$

Now a review of all the stresses that have been known to occur on motion simulators is specified. This defines a limited medical risk scenario in which a pilot can safely be exposed to without any observed compromise in his ability to perform the mission.

Extant Capabilities of Motion Simulators:

The last data base considered in this paper was derived from a study of existing motion simulators which have been known to have minimum medical risk. The philosophy was that if a previous motion simulator had run human subjects without known medical mishaps, then one could presume this was at least a safe scenario to test humans in complex acceleration fields.

A survey was conducted of past experiments [17] which included the centrifuges at Wright Patterson Air Force Base, at Brooks Air Force Base, and the Navy centrifuge at NADC in Pennsylvania. Also incorporated in this data base were a number of medical studies of humans in unusual acceleration environments such as a cardiovascular investigation in which the subjects had z axis rotation of up to 720 deg/sec for 3 minutes, studies in spatial disorientation, and animal studies conducted by the Russians. A respected reference in this area which addresses the early known history of such medical risk is the book by Dehart [19]. The summary of all these previous data became a basis for the Air Force definition of complex G accelerations and rotations for human stress. This standard has been incorporated into the generic protocol for use in running subjects today [18]. A summary of these data is as follows:

$$-2 G < G_z < 9.5 G \quad (51)$$

$$-6.5 G < G_x < 6.5 G \quad (52)$$

$$-4 G < G_y < 4 G \quad (53)$$

$$-5 G/sec < \dot{G}_z < 5 G/sec \quad (54)$$

$$-5 G/sec < \dot{G}_x < 5 G/sec \quad (55)$$

$$-2 G/sec < \dot{G}_y < 2 G/sec \quad (56)$$

for z axis rotation:

$$-90 \text{ deg/sec} \leq \dot{\theta}_x \leq 90 \text{ deg/sec} \quad (57)$$

$$-10 \text{ deg/sec}^2 \leq \alpha_x = \ddot{\theta}_x \leq 10 \text{ deg/sec}^2 \quad (58)$$

for y axis rotation:

$$-90 \text{ deg/sec} \leq \dot{\theta}_y \leq 90 \text{ deg/sec} \quad (59)$$

$$-10 \text{ deg/sec}^2 \leq \alpha_y = \ddot{\theta}_y \leq 10 \text{ deg/sec}^2 \quad (60)$$

for x axis rotation:

$$-90 \text{ deg/sec} \leq \dot{\theta}_x \leq 90 \text{ deg/sec} \quad (61)$$

$$-10 \text{ deg/sec}^2 \leq \alpha_x = \ddot{\theta}_x \leq 10 \text{ deg/sec}^2 \quad (62)$$

It is noted that these numbers were based on conservative estimates since little medical risk was desired to be explored outside the region of former sustained acceleration tolerance limits. The results of all four studies can now be summarized.

Summary of All Four Data Bases

For notational simplicity, let:

Study 1 = The X-29 and X-31 aircraft data.

Study 2 = The Cobra maneuver (1989 Paris Airshow and computer simulations).

Study 3 = F-15 prototypes flown in Israel with dynamic scaling.

Study 4 = A survey of previous ground base motion simulator studies [17] with limited medical risk.

WCS = A worst case scenario design.

With respect to the body axis system in figure (1), the terms G_x , G_y , G_z , \dot{G}_x , \dot{G}_y , \dot{G}_z are understood. Let $\dot{\theta}_p$ and $\ddot{\theta}_p$ refer to the body pitch axis, $\dot{\theta}_r, \ddot{\theta}_r$ refer to the body roll axis, and $\dot{\theta}_y$ and $\ddot{\theta}_y$ refer to the body yaw axis. All angular measurements are in degrees, degrees/second and degrees/second². The summary of all four studies are displayed in Table I:

Thus the right most column of Table I illustrates the worst case scenario for motion simulators.

Summary and Conclusions

A survey of all existing motion fields was obtained to set a basis for simulation of supermaneuverable flight on a centrifuge simulator when it is

Table I - Summary of All Four Data Bases (High and Low Values)

Study No. Variable	1	2	3	4	WCS
G_x	.6, .04	2.2, -2.5	.3, -1.7	6.5, -6.5	6.5, -6.5
G_y	.7, -.16	0	-	4, -4	4, -4
G_z	3.6, .41	3.0, -1	7, -2	9.5, -2	9.5, -2
\dot{G}_x	-	-	-	± 5	± 5
\dot{G}_y	-	-	-	± 2	± 2
\dot{G}_z	-	-	-	± 5	± 5
$\dot{\theta}_p$	11, -34	120, 0	180, -170	± 90	180, -170
$\ddot{\theta}_p$	289, -253	38, -38	-	± 10	289, -253
$\dot{\theta}_r$	25, -34	30, 0	40, -150	± 90	90, -150
$\ddot{\theta}_r$	289, -253	20, -20	-	± 10	289, -253
$\dot{\theta}_y$	4, -27	0	0	± 90	± 90
$\ddot{\theta}_y$	69, -68	0	0	± 10	69, -68

modeled as a robotic system. The extant data used in the survey included operational definitions of motion fields as well as prototype data and also data representing minimum medical risk to human subjects. The design of centrifuge simulators can now proceed with knowledge of these existing data presented herein.

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Figure (1) - The Body Axis Coordinate System

Axes and notation.

Aircraft orientation: the Euler attitude angles and rotation sequence.

Figure (3) From [14]

Figure (4)

F-16 SIMULATION OF COBRA MANEUVER (SKOW, 1990)

Tradeoff of G_x to G_z
For The Cobra Supermaneuver

Figure (5)

— G_x - - - G_z ($1G=32.2 \text{ ft/s}^2$)

Cobra Maneuver
 $G_x, G_z, \text{ and } G_{\text{Total}} = \sqrt{G_x^2 + G_z^2}$

Figure (6)

— G_x - - - G_z x G_{total}